

ASSESSING TEMPORAL PERFORMANCE OF CORDEX-SEA RAINFALL SIMULATIONS AGAINST ERA5 DATA

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Abstract

Modeling precipitation poses a significant challenge for climate models. The CORDEX-SEA simulations offer the most comprehensive set of high-resolution regional climate models for Southeast Asia. However, there is a notable gap in the research literature regarding the evaluation of rainfall model performance in these simulations. Most evaluations focus on the spatial aspect, with limited attention given to temporal aspect evaluations. This research endeavors to evaluate the performance of nine CORDEX-SEA rainfall simulations in comparison to ERA5 data. The assessment considered temporal aspects and employed Taylor's skill score to measure model performance. The results showed that no model consistently performs well across all aspects and regions of investigation. However, the NorESM1_d model frequently outperforms others, followed by HadGEM2_a and HadGEM2_c. Most models in the South China Sea region and half of the models in the Indonesian region have low performance. Based on the annual cycle correlation and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis, the ensemble mean of CORDEX-SEA outperforms all models, but not in the trend and wavelet analysis. These findings provide valuable insights into the selection of appropriate rainfall models for climate projection analyses across Southeast Asia based on temporal analysis.

Keywords: CORDEX-SEA Simulations, Performance Evaluation, Rainfall Models.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Southeast Asian region faces a greater risk from changing weather patterns, including more frequent and intense extreme events in the future (Ge et al., 2019; Hijioka et al., 2014). Understanding these changes relies on studying the atmosphere and related factors. Climate models are used to make projections about future climate conditions (Hausfather et al., 2020). These models are essential for studying how the climate responds to different factors (Flato et al., 2013). However, the resolution of global climate models (GCMs) is still coarse, having order of a few hundred kilometers, which limits their suitability for regional climate impact studies (Gao & Giorgi, 2017; Giorgi et al., 2009). For a higher resolution (about 25 km), the Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment-Southeast Asia (CORDEX-SEA) was completed in 2018 (Tangang et al., 2018). These regional climate models (RCMs) are expected to enhance the reliability of climate impact studies in Southeast Asia (Tangang et al., 2020; Tangang et al., 2019; Giorgi, 2019; Lee et al., 2018), even though the main factor contributing to errors in certain region is not necessarily the low spatial resolution (Ashfaq et al., 2016).

In a study conducted by Tangang et al. (2020), a comparison was made between the multi-model ensemble mean (MME) of CORDEX-SEA and GCMs. The findings unveiled that

CORDEX-SEA simulation outputs, known for their higher resolutions, demonstrated superior performance in comparison to GCMs. Among studies that evaluate the models in the CORDEX-SEA (Tangang et al., 2020; Tangang et al., 2019; Tuyet et al., 2019), they use observational datasets with resolutions (50 km) which is much coarser than those of the models (25 km), and all the data are regridded to the coarser resolution to ensure a fair comparison. This regridding process might reduce some of the small details produced by the model with a 25 km resolution (Tangang et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2019). Hence, evaluation using a reference with a resolution that matches more closely with the models is potentially more adequate. Furthermore, significant differences exist among observational datasets in this area (Juneng et al., 2016; Brunner et al., 2019). In various regions worldwide, including Southeast Asia, many studies have documented significant variations among these gridded precipitation datasets (Ceglar et al., 2017). The most notable limitation of gridded observational-based data occurs when dealing with mountainous regions, where interpolation technique might not be reliable due to the very limited number of gauges in those areas (Borges et al., 2016). Hence, using a dataset based on a limited number of gauges as a reference in evaluating a model in a region might yield inappropriate results. In recent decades, climate reanalysis data have found extensive application across various fields, including the prediction of precipitation (Kim et al., 2019), as they bridge the gap between the need for precipitation estimates and the scarcity of gauge observations in certain regions (Lavers et al., 2022). The well-known reanalysis products, ERA5, the latest global climate reanalysis data from the European Centre for Medium Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), integrates extensive historical observations worldwide through advanced modeling and data assimilation systems (Jiao et al., 2021). Numerous studies have demonstrated that, among the various global atmospheric reanalysis products produced by different groups, ERA5 consistently stands out as one of the top-performing options (Vanella et al., 2022; Tarek et al., 2020; Zandler et al., 2020).

Considering the ERA5's finer resolution (25 km) and its well-established quality, this study aims to compare the similarity of CORDEX-SEA output models (25 km resolution) against ERA5 in simulating precipitation during the historical period spanning from 1976 to 2005. The comparison encompasses temporal aspects of rainfall across the land of Southeast Asian region. The outcomes of this study are anticipated to provide insights when comparing the models to ERA5, choosing suitable models for climate projections, and other related usage in the Southeast Asia region.

2. DATA AND METHODS

This study conducted a comparative analysis between nine RCMs sourced from CORDEX-SEA rainfall simulations and ERA5 data. The latest version (2018) of the CORDEX-SEA datasets was utilized, downscaled from GCMs participating in the CMIP5 project. CORDEX-SEA datasets based on CMIP6 are not yet available. The study focuses on the Southeast Asian domain, which spans from 90.5°E to 145°E longitude and 14.5°S to 25.5°N latitude (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Topographical map of Southeast Asia region

The climate model data under evaluation consisted of monthly historical precipitation spanning from 1976 to 2005, with a spatial resolution of 0.22 degree (about 25 km). This research focused on assessing the performance of the models against ERA5 within land-only regions. A detailed description of the models is provided in Table 1 and for the reference data is presented in Table 2.

Table 1: Description of climate models.

No	GCMs (driving model)		RCMs (dynamical downscaler)		Grid (lat, lon)	Model ID
	Institusi	Model	Institusi	Model		
1	CNRM (France)	CNRM-CM5	SMHI (Sweden)	RCA4	194, 264	CNRM_a
2	EC-Earth (Europe)	EC-EARTH	ICTP (Italy)	RegCM4-3	191, 253	ECE_b
3	NOAA (United States)	GFDL-ESM2M	ICTP	RegCM4-3	191, 253	GFDL_b
4	IPSL (France)	IPSL-CM5ALR	ICTP	RegCM4-3	191, 253	IPSL_b
5	Hadley Centre (UK)	HadGEM2-ES	SMHI (Sweden)	RCA4	194, 264	HadGEM2_a
6	Hadley Centre (UK)	HadGEM2-ES	ICTP	RegCM4-7	189, 335	HadGEM2_c
7	Hadley Centre (UK)	HadGEM2-ES	GERICS (Germany)	REMO2015	201, 273	HadGEM2_d
8	MPI (Jerman)	MPI-ESM-MR	ICTP	RegCM4-7	189, 335	MPI_c
9	NCC (Norway)	NorESM1-M	GERITZ	REMO2015	201, 273	NorESM1_d

Obtaining reference data at a resolution similar to the models being assessed (0.22 degree) presents a challenge. Therefore, ERA5 (0.25 degree) was used as the reference dataset (Hersbach et al., 2020), and to ensure a fair comparison, all datasets were regridded to the reference resolution (0.25 degree). Tangang et al. (2020) used ERA5 and GPCC as the main references when assessing the CORDEX-SEA simulations performance. Numerous studies

have highlighted the benefits of ERA5 as a reference dataset, not solely due to its higher resolution, but also its comparable quality (Vanella et al., 2022; Jiao et al., 2021; Tarek et al., 2020).

Table 2: Description of reference data

Dataset	Product	Spatial covered	Time covered**)	Resolution	Reference
ERA5 (https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu)	Averaged reanalysis	Land Ocean	1976-2005 Monthly	0.25°	(Hersbach et al., 2020)
GPCP (https://esgf-node.llnl.gov/search/obs4mips)	v7-7A	Land Ocean	1979-2017 Monthly	2.5°	(Adler et al., 2018)

The assessment process began by inspecting the data input for minimum and maximum values to detect any outliers that might indicate computational errors or other technical issues. These anomalies could arise in regional climate models (RCMs) due to the downscaling process. Next, Taylor metric (equation 1) was used to quantitatively measure how close the models agree with the reference dataset (Taylor, 2001) in terms of various temporal aspects, including annual cycle, trend, wavelet, and Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analysis.

$$S = \frac{4(1+r)}{(\sigma_r+1/\sigma_r)^2 (1+r_0)} \quad (1)$$

For this equations, r is the correlation coefficient between the observed and simulated data, r_0 is the maximum correlation (set to be 1), σ_r is the standard deviation ratio between the simulated and observed data. The data analysis instrument of this study used Python programming which was the result of coding modifications from the application of open source RCMES (Regional Climate Models Evaluation System) which can be downloaded from <https://rcmes.jpl.nasa.gov> (Kim et al. 2014; Lee et al. 2018). The modifications made, first to overcome error that occurs when running program (due to some coding syntax that does not match the version of the supporting application). Second, the addition of several aspects of model evaluation, namely: point-to-poin temporal correlation, wavelet analysis, Fast Fourier Transform (FFT), and clustering of rainfall patterns using the non-hierarchical (k-means clustering) and hierarchical clustering. This research begins by validating the input data, namely checking the minimum and maximum values on the input data. This is to ensure the absence of extreme data and/or outlier which is related to computational technical errors and is not the result of natural processes that occur due to atmospheric dynamics. Furthermore, the spatial and temporal performance of the model was measured using Taylor metric which quantitatively measured how close the model results were to the reference data (Taylor, 2001). The advantage of this metric or Taylor score over other metrics is that this metric is a combination of two parameters, namely correlation and standard deviation. In the context of the rainfall time series data used in this study, correlation is a measure of the variability pattern and the standard deviation is a measure of its amplitude. Performance measurements were carried out on spatial aspects,

namely regional, zonal and meridional averages. For the temporal aspect, performance measurements were first carried out at each grid point in Southeast Asia with annual rainfall cycle data. Second, trend measurement is carried out using the original Mann-Kendall (MK) test (Um *et al.* 2017; Narayanan *et al.* 2013). To overcome the possibility of autocorrelation effects in time series data (which can produce inaccurate trends), a modified MK test is also used, namely the pre-whitened Mann Kendall test (PWMK) (Supari *et al.*, 2017). In general, the procedure of this research is presented in Figure 2.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Input data validation

The results of input data validation and pre-evaluation, which involve checking the maximum and minimum values, are presented in Table 3. This step is crucial for identifying extreme values that are not due to natural processes but rather fall into the category of computational errors or other technical issues. Generally, this is due to the existence of relaxation zones used in the dynamic downscaling process from a global scale model to a regional or local scale (Giorgi, 2019). If this relaxation zone still exists in the model dataset then it needs to be excluded, because the purpose of this study is to evaluate the valid data. Among the 9 models used, it was found that the IPSL_b and GFDL_b models had abnormal maximum rainfall values (caused by the relaxation zone effect) at the lateral domain boundary. In this study, in order to avoid errors of such a thing in the later stages of analysis, the evaluation domain needs to be shifted to latitude and longitude boundaries that are free of such errors. In addition, checking the minimum value is also important in identifying the amount of invalid rainfall, namely if it has a negative value. Among the 9 models, some exhibit negative values, but these are of very small magnitude (on the order of E-10) and are thus insignificant.

Table 3: Minimum and maximum values on input data

Model Name	Min (mm/month) (mm/mo)	Max (mm/month)
ERA5	6.94E-15	97.80
GPCP	-3.2E-16	40.67
CNRM_a	-9.4E-16	171.38
ECE_b	0	276.59
IPSL_b	0	112.96
HadGEM2_d	1.33E-12	378.73
HadGEM2_c	0	299.88
HadGEM2_a	-1.8E-15	160.72
MPI_c	0	270.59
NorESM1_d	5.34E-10	210.44
GFDL_b	0	312.45

3.2 Temporal performance

This section explores the evaluation of the model's performance on the temporal aspect by directly comparing (point to point) the time series data on the grid in the model with the grid in the reference dataset (ERA5) with two time scales (monthly and yearly cycles).

For the annual cycle (Figure 2), this shows a more visible/obvious variation in performance scores across the grid than on a monthly scale that shows very low results. From Figure 2, it appears that quantitatively (based on Taylor's score) the CNRM_a model produces the highest average score (0.31) among other single models, followed by NorESM1_d (0.29) and GFDL_b (0.29). Although the two models have the same Taylor score, their average scores differ, with values of 0.48 and 0.49, making the GFDL_b model higher.

Additionally, based on visual observations compared to the reference data map (GPCP), GFDL_b shows a higher resemblance compared to NorESM1_d. For the ensemble mean (MME), it outperforms other models with score 0.39. Furthermore, the results of the quantitative and qualitative evaluations of the model's performance are compared in Table 4.

In addition, as shown in Figure 2, among all the models the most distinct pattern is in the northern region of Southeast Asia (10° to 23°N) where the IPSL model has a very low score (in line with a study by Aminoto et al., 2024) while most other models have high scores. In addition, the surrounding South China Sea region (Peninsular Malay, Serawak, Brunei, Sabah and the Philippines) is a region where all models consistently have low temporal performance scores.

This indicates that most models have difficulty simulating rainfall in the region. Some of the following research results are related to this. Tangang et al. (2020) states that Southeast Asia's climate is difficult to simulate due to its complex geography, including many islands, vast oceans, and varied topography. Juneng et al. (2016) using the RegCM4 model with various types of parameterization stated that the model had difficulty in simulating rainfall in equatorial areas (including mountainous areas).

The more specific causes for the region are most likely related to the phenomenon Borneo vortex (BV) that frequently appears around the South China Sea greatly affects the rainfall anomalies in the region and is a challenge for most models to capture the phenomenon.

Koseki & Teo (2014) mentioned that BV is an important factor on the climate in the region because it affects the convergence of humidity at low levels, leading to significant increases in rainfall and convective rainfall mesoscale intense near the center of BV.

Figure 2: Plot of the model's temporal performance at each coordinate point in the land and ocean region of Southeast Asia, the value in parentheses is the model's similarity score to the observation data (GPCP), the value of m indicates the average value of Taylor's score, red and blue colors indicate high and low performance

Table 4: Comparison of performance based on quantitative and qualitative aspects

Model	Quantitative evaluation (with Taylor's score average/ranking)		Qualitative evaluation (by comparing the results of Taylor's score in each sub-region)	
			Region with high score (0,6 - 1,0)	Region with low score (0,0 - 0,4)
MME	0.39	1	Same as CNRM_a but higher in northern Southeast Asia	Similar to CNRM_a but higher in Peninsular Malay
CNRM_a	0.31	2	Parts of northern Southeast Asia Sumatra Island Java Borneo	Peninsular Malay Aceh Sarawak, Brunei, Sabah Irian Jaya
HadGEM2_a	0.30	3	Same as CNRM_a but higher in northern Southeast Asia	Same with CNRM_a
NorESM1_d	0,29	4	Same with MPI_c	Same as MPI_c except Java
GFDL_b	0.29	5	Same with MPI_c South Borneo	Same as MPI_c except South Borneo
ECE_b	0.29	6	Parts of northern Southeast Asia Java	Peninsular Malay Sarawak, Brunei, Sabah Indonesian Islands
HadGEM2_d	0.28	7	Same with CNRM_a	Same with CNRM_a Part of Java
HadGEM2_c	0.28	8	Same with CNRM_a	Same with CNRM_a However, in South Borneo it is lower
MPI_c	0.23	9	Northern Southeast Asia Java	Peninsular Malay Sarawak, Brunei, Sabah Indonesian Islands
IPSL_b	0.07	10	Monsoon rainfall pattern areas: Lampung, South Borneo, Java	Northern Southeast Asia Peninsular Malay Sarawak, Brunei, Sabah

Another study on BV suggests that rainfall deficits can be attributed to the inability of models to accurately simulate complex circulation and rainfall dynamics in this region, as mentioned by Tangang et al. (2020). In the research by Hole et al. (2021), mentioning that accurately simulating BV is a challenge for current climate models and the need for higher model resolution (25 km and below). The results of his research using the HadGEM3 model (GCM, 25 km) show that the model is able to simulate BV well. The similarity of the model with the HadGEM2 model (RCM, 25 km) used in this study is only in resolution and differs greatly in relation to other parameters. The results of temporal analysis of the three types of HadGEM2 (Figure 12) in the BV-affected region show that HadGEM2_d (from RCM REMO) has the highest similarity to the reference data (ERA5), followed by HadGEM2_a (from RCM RCA4).

For the performance of the next temporal aspect, namely the analysis of rainfall trends, it is carried out by comparing model data with references related to patterns of increase, decrease or absence of rainfall trends (Endo et al., 2009). This analysis involves the Mann-Kendall test on monthly or annual rainfall time series data at each grid point of the study area. The results for the monthly time scale mostly show low similarity to the reference data. For annual time

scales, it shows higher similarity. According to the evaluation of the temporal aspects of the trend (Figure 3), the results of some models are very similar to the reference (ERA5). When comparing the results of trend analysis in Borneo, the findings are in line with the results presented by Sukmara et al. (2022), which show a significant upward trend in the southern part of Borneo (the study used MEERA rainfall data).

Figure 3: The trend plot of the average annual rainfall on the model and ERA5 uses the MK (top) and PWMK (bottom) tests for the statistical significance of the p-value < 0.05, the red color indicates an increasing trend and the blue on the contrary, the values in the parentheses express the similarity score of the model to ERA5

Figure 3 also shows that the trend analysis using the MK and PMK tests on the same data generally results in slight differences for certain regions. This suggests that the autocorrelation

effect is minimal, leading to only minor discrepancies between the two tests. In the ERA5 data for the island of Central Kalimantan, the Constitutional Court test indicates a significant upward trend. However, the FMD test reveals that the area with an upward trend is quite limited. Notably, the color pattern of the image (trend) tends to form a west-east longitudinal pattern rather than a north-south one. This distinctive pattern highlights areas with a p-value of < 0.05 , indicating a statistically significant trend at a 95% confidence level.

3.3 Wavelet and FFT analysis

This section (Figure 4) examines the seasonal to interannual variability of rainfall in the model using wavelet analysis (Jiang et al. 2013; Chao et al. 2014). This method is superior, in certain respects, to the spectral analysis used by Siew et al. (2014). In this case, the wavelet is formed from the time series of average precipitation anomalies. To quantitatively measure the similarity of the model with the reference data, the Taylor performance score is used, and the results are presented on each wavelet graph to facilitate the ease of comparing their similarity.

Figure 4: Wavelet plot of rainfall variability in Southeast Asia on the CORDEX-SEA model. The T value expresses the model's similarity score to the reference (ERA5)

In Figure 4 it appears that most of the variability modes are concentrated in three dominant patterns (monsoon, ENSO, PDO) with periodicity of about 1, 2-8, and 16 years. The periodicity of ENSO 2-8 years is slightly different from that of Siew et al. (2014) which states 2-5 years based on GPCP data (version v2.2) as a reference. It also appears that GPCP and ERA5 show an almost identical pattern with a similarity score of 0.94. However, for the average type of ensemble, all of them have low similarity. These findings warrant further investigation because the ensemble average generally has a performance that outperforms all individual models in most cases through 'canceling error' among the models that occur during the average operation (Hagedorn et al. 2005; Walker et al. 2014). For individual models, HadGEM2_a (0.44), followed by NorESM1_d (0.40). In contrast, the CNRM_a model, which previously often demonstrated superior capabilities, in this wavelet plot had a relatively low score (0.31). The low performance score of the ensemble mean (MME) likely due to the effect of rainfall

averaging in the Southeast Asian region which is of course very wide so that there is a large difference in temporal variability between the sub-regions (those that are close to the equator and those that are far from the equator). The effect that can arise is the mutual elimination or weakening of the rainfall curves that have opposite phases between the averaged rainfall models. As a result, the average variability between years is weak/small.

To see the comparison of the results of the wavelet analysis plot for a large region (Southeast Asia, very diverse rainfall patterns) with a small area (Sumatra sub R1 and R2, the rainfall pattern is mostly the same), the wavelet plot is presented in Figures 5 and 6. The boundaries of the sub-region were determined based on the approximation of the division of sub-regions in Southeast Asia in the previous study (Tangang et al. 2020; Juneng et al. 2016; Aldrian and Susanto 2003). The determination of the results of the sub-regional boundaries using the clustering of rainfall patterns carried out in the previous part is not used here, this is considering that most models do not have sufficient similarity in the cluster results in accordance with the reference data (ERA5 and GPCP).

Figure 5: Wavelet plot for the Sumatra region in sub-region R1 (6°LU–EQ and 95° – 104°E)

The wavelet plot for the Sumatra region shows that the wavelet mode in the period of one year or more seems rather clear in MME ensemble. This is different from the previous results (Figure 4) where the wavelet mode mode in the period of one year or more is not clearly visible. In addition, in the wavelet plot in the Sumatra R1 region, there is also a wavelet mode in the 1/2 year period which is a characteristic of the equatorial rainfall pattern which has two rainfall peaks in a year (Aldrian and Susanto 2003). In these results, the equatorial rainfall pattern is clearly visible in the ERA5, GPCP, and most models (Figure 5), but it is slightly less visible in

the Sumatra R2 (Figure 6). Regarding the performance of individual model, it shows that the CNRM_a model, previously had low performance (0.31) due to data averaging in the Southeast Asia region, in the wavelet plot of the Sumatra R1 region showed an increase in performance to 0.47 (Figure 5) and 0.54 (Figure 6). This also happens with other models. Likewise, for ensemble mean that previously had low similarity values, it has a higher score (0.39) in the Sumatra R1 domain (Figure 5), and 0.64 in R2 (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Wavelet plot for the Sumatra region in the R2 sub-region (EQ – 6° LU and 99° – 106° E)

To compare the results of the wavelet analysis plot with another method, the FFT plot is presented (Figure 7 for the Southeast Asia region and Figure 8 for the R1 and R2 of Sumatera region).

This FFT plot generally shows higher score results compared to the results obtained from wavelet plot analysis. For R1, the ensemble mean has the highest similarity score (0.76), surpassing all individual models, with IPSL_b being the top-performing individual model with a score of 0.74. For R2, the results are similar but with even higher scores.

The FFT plot results for two different regions (Southeast Asia and Sumatra, sub-regions) also show a large difference in the plot results, namely the inter-annual variability curve appears large in the Southeast Asian region but appears small for the R1 and R2 regions.

This difference in results was caused by the magnitude of the seasonal (intra-annual) and inter-annual curves being almost the same in the Southeast Asian region, while in the R1 and R2 regions the two were very different, which caused the inter-annual variability curve to appear weak/small. In both figures, the magnitude of the interannual variability curve is actually the same (i.e. 0.1-0.5).

Figure 7: FFT plot for the models (red) vs reference (black) of rainfall anomalies in Southeast Asia, the values in the parentheses express the pattern similarity score of models to the reference (ERA5)

Figure continues to the next page

Figure 8: FFT plot for the models (red) and reference (black) of rainfall anomalies in Sumatra R1 (top) and R2 (bottom) sub-regions, the values in the parentheses express the similarity score of the pattern to the reference (ERA5)

The difference in the results of the wavelet and FFT methods needs to be investigated further. The possibility is due to the scale on the wavelet plot being less low or due to the factor of less/more sensitive to low values. After reducing the scale of the wavelet plot, the plot results in ensemble mean began to be clear. This is due to the reduction in scale only has an impact on visualization and not on the calculation of performance scores. Further investigation showed that the difference is caused by the difference in calculating amplitude, in the wavelet the amplitude is calculated by square (the positive number is less than 1 if squared, the result will be much smaller) while in FFT it is not squared. A summary of the diverse capabilities of individual models and ensemble is presented in Table 5. A model that has the same or a slightly lower score than the best model is included in the summary as a comparison.

Table 5: Summary of the models and ensemble mean performance

Performance evaluation aspect	Ensemble mean's score	Model's score	Figure
Annual cycle	0.39	CNRM_a NorESM1_d GFDL_b	2
Trend using MK test	0.59	GFDL_b IPSL_b	3
Trend using PMK test	0.50	IPSL_b NorESM1_d	3
Wavelet (Southeast Asia)	0.16	HadGEM2_a NorESM1_d	4
Wavelet (Sumatra R1)	0.39	HadGEM2_a MPI_c	5
Wavelet (Sumatra R2)	0.64	HadGEM2_a HadGEM2_c	6
FFT (Southeast Asia)	0.76	IPSL_b HadGEM2_a HadGEM2_d WE_Taylor	7
FFT (Sumatra R1)	0.93	IPSL_b HadGEM2_c	8
FFT (Sumatra R2)	0.92	CNRM_a HadGEM2_a	8

Table 5 reveals that, temporally, no model consistently performs well across all aspects and regions of investigation. However, the NorESM1_d model frequently outperforms others. Additionally, spatially, the CNRM_a model often performs better than others, aligning with the findings of other studies (Tuyet et al. 2019; Siew et al. 2014).

4. CONCLUSION

This study evaluates the performance of nine CORDEX-SEA rainfall simulations against ERA5 data. The assessment focuses on temporal aspects and utilizes Taylor's skill score to

gauge model performance. The findings indicate that no model excels consistently across all aspects and regions. However, the NorESM1_d model often outperforms others, with HadGEM2_a and HadGEM2_c following closely. Most models perform poorly in the South China Sea region, and about half show low performance in the Indonesian region. The ensemble mean of CORDEX-SEA surpasses all individual models based on annual cycle correlation and fast Fourier transform analysis, though not in trend and wavelet analysis. These results offer valuable insights for selecting suitable rainfall models for climate projection analyses in Southeast Asia.

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